

A Study of Job Satisfaction among College Teachers with Special Reference to Constituent Colleges in Patna District

Pooja

Research Scholar, Department of Commerce and Business Administration, L.N. Mithila University, Darbhanga, INDIA

Corresponding Author: poojasm2009@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study examined the development of education in India. All the factors which influence excellence in the field of education are the quality, competence and character of teachers apart from the infrastructure, cognitive and non-cognitive qualities of students and parental support.

Keywords— Education, Population, Development in India

the whole family gets educate and when the whole family educates the whole society educates and consequently the whole nation.

Education is considered as the base of a nation's development. It improves productive capacity, adds to one's self-esteem, and transforms human beings into human capital. These, in turn, facilitate to build the backbone of a nation. Bihar has a long history of education dating back to the days of the Nalanda University. But, ironically, in the post-independence era Bihar has been one of the laggard states in education. In recent times, however, the state has improved significantly in the education sector.

As per details from Census 2011, Bihar has population of 10.38 Crore, an increase from figure of 8.30 Crore in 2001 census. Total population of Bihar as per 2011 census is 103,804,637 of which male and female are 54,185,347 and 49,619,290 respectively. In 2001, total population was 82,998,509 in which males were 43,243,795 while females were 39,754,714. The total population growth in this decade was 25.07 percent while in previous decade it was 28.43 percent. The population of Bihar forms 8.58 percent of India in 2011. In 2001, the figure was 8.07 percent. A brief detail regarding population, literacy, etc. of Bihar has been given below:

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is the flower that fragrant the whole nation with the blow of happiness and peace and makes enable the persons to raise their sense, skill and living standard. When it blooms in full the whole society will be civilized and developed. Education is reasonably a good indicator of economic development which means that the development of the country can be measured through the development of education. The right of every individual to education is one of the first provisions of the Universal Declaration on Human Rights and education is considered to be most important one. The importance of education can be realized from this fact which is most popular among the people that when a women educates

Table - 1.1
Educational Indicators & Population in Bihar

S.N.	Description	2011	2001
1	Approximate Population	10.38 Crore	8.30 Crore
2	Actual Population	103,804,637	82,998,509
3	Male	54,185,347	43,243,795
4	Female	49,619,290	39,754,714
5	Population Growth	25.07%	28.43%
6	Percentage of total Population	8.58%	8.07%
7	Sex ratio	916	921
8	Child sex ratio	933	908
9	Literacy	63.82%	47.00%
10	Male literacy	73.39	59.68
11	Female literacy	53.33	33.12
12	Total literate	54390254	31109577
12	Male literate	32711975	20644376
13	Female literate	21678279	10465201

Source: Census Report, 2001 and 2011

Literacy represents a measure of educational status of any community. Literacy rate in

estimated as the percentage of people educated to the respective total population. Though literacy is very

important for both males and females, these exists a wide gap between both the sexes in India. The trends in total

literacy rates by sex in India between the years 1981 and 2011 are given below:

Table No. – 1.2
Trends in Literacy Rates by Sex in India: 1981-2011

Particulars	1981	1991	2001	2011
Male	56.37	64.13	75.85	82.14
Female	29.75	39.29	54.16	65.46
Total	43.56	52.20	65.38	74.04

Source: Registrar General of India, Census of India

The total literacy rate in India during the year 1981 was 43.56 per cent which increased steadily and reached to 74.04 per cent by 2011. Though there is an increase in the literacy rate, it provides us a clue that there is still scope for further developing the literacy levels as the maximum achievable limit is 100. When we looked at the literacy rate by male and female separately, interesting observations could be made. In all the years, male literacy rates were higher than that of female literacy rates. In the year 1981, the male literacy rate was 56 per cent while the same for female was only 29.75 per cent. In the year 2011, the male literacy rate has reached to 82.14 per cent and female literacy rate to 65.46 per cent.

Bihar is responsible for preserving the glorious history of the state as used to be in the golden era of Nalanda University and Vikramshila University. The department is concerned with providing education and setting up related frames and infrastructure across the state. With five directorates and several apex bodies, the department has been working to create facilitative environment in which youth, women and others would explore their knowledge and skills by pursuing primary, secondary, higher and mass education.

The progress of nation in different spheres of life depends upon the quality of its people, which in turn depends upon how well the younger generation is moulded by parents, teachers and education system as a whole. Students are one of the important assets of any society. Well-being of society depends upon its students because these are the people who will take the responsibility of the success of the society in future and in achieving this goal teacher's role is extremely important. The Education Commission (1964-66) has rightly remarked that, "The destiny of India is now being shaped in her classroom".

The importance of a teacher in the educational process is unquestionable. However, the entire edifice of education becomes shaky if the teacher is weak and ineffective. An effective teacher is amongst the foremost factors contributing to educational improvement, which we are trying hard to achieve. Every teaching faculties know that even a balanced curriculum remains useless unless or until imparted into life by the right kind of teachers and suitable method of teaching and by the well satisfied teachers. Therefore, all the factors which influence excellence in the field of education are the

quality, competence and character of teachers apart from the infrastructure, cognitive and non-cognitive qualities of students and parental support. So nothing is important than attracting calibre person to the teaching profession and providing them with the best possible professional training and creating congenial environment of work, in which they can become fully effective and satisfied. When teachers are satisfied with their job they can perform their responsibilities with more concentration and devotion. Therefore, satisfaction is needed in the behaviour of a college teacher if he/she has to perform productive activities in the college.

Job satisfaction is very difficult to define because the concept of satisfaction is highly subjective. It varies from person to person. Locke (1976) gives a comprehensive definition of job satisfaction as involving cognitive, affective and evaluative reactions or attitudes and states it is "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience". It results from the perception that one's job fulfils or allows the fulfilment of one's important job values, providing and to the degree that these values are congruent with one's needs. Employees satisfaction is affected by several aspects of the job, including job security, pay, working conditions, opportunity for advancement. Job attitudes are therefore determined jointly by job characteristics as well as employee characteristics.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

As compared to other levels of educational system in the society, higher education has a much bigger role to play. Being at higher level of the educational pyramid and thus able to influence other levels of education, and having wider access to all available knowledge, it can undoubtedly operate as a powerful instrument to help the process of social change in Indian society. It nurtures the competency of future leadership in the students who hold the potential to develop the society. It prepares them to successfully carry out different responsibilities for social, economic and political development. Higher education is 'higher' also because it is at the frontier of knowledge trying to further expand these frontiers.

College Teachers are arguably the most important group of professionals for our nation's future.

Therefore, it is disturbing to find that many of today's teachers in higher education are dissatisfied with their jobs. Job satisfaction is good not only for employees but society as a whole. It increases productivity and classroom performance in the college. These aspects are important in higher education in India. The government of India is highly concerned to provide quality education at college level. But without job satisfaction among the behaviour of the college teachers, the objective of providing quality education would not be materialized. Therefore, job satisfaction is needed among college teachers to promote quality education.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- 1) To know the level of job satisfaction of the college teachers with respect to; designations, gender, income, earning members in the family and family size.
- 2) To know, whether female college teachers are more satisfied than male college teachers or not.
- 3) To identify the factors which impact the job satisfaction of the college teachers.
- 4) To suggest appropriate measures to improve the level of satisfaction.

IV. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to know the factors impacting job satisfaction among the college teachers in Patna, because, it may have a direct effect on student learning of the colleges. Considering the possible correlation between teacher job satisfaction and the quality of student instruction/teaching, it is important to understand the factors that may affect job satisfaction. Most of the research of job satisfaction is related to management of industrial, banking and business organization. The study on college teachers' job satisfaction is not many. Hence, more research is needed in college teachers' job satisfaction, if we are interested to provide quality education to our students at the college level. This study is hoped to contribute to that extent.

V. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following research hypotheses were formulated to direct the study:

HYPOTHESIS 1- There is no significant relationship between the Designation of the College Teachers and their level of satisfaction.

HYPOTHESIS 2- Female College Teachers are more satisfied with their job than their male counterpart.

HYPOTHESIS 3 -There is no significant relationship between the income per annum and the level of satisfaction.

HYPOTHESIS 4- There is no significant relationship between the family size and the level of satisfaction.

HYPOTHESIS 5- There is no significant relationship between the Earning Members in the Family and their level of satisfaction.

HYPOTHESIS 6-There is no significant relation between teaching experience and their level of satisfaction.

HYPOTHESIS 7-There is no significant relation between opportunities for promotion/Professional Growth of the college teacher and their level of satisfaction.

VI. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

TYPE OF RESEARCH

This study is an empirical research and based on the survey method.

SOURCE OF INFORMATION

Primary Data: The source of information is mainly primary and the data collected through questionnaire from the college teachers working in constituent colleges in Patna district.

Secondary Data: Work of eminent scholars already published in various journals related to job satisfaction and related data collected.

The target population of this study consists of teachers of the constituent colleges in Patna District and the size of the sample was 150 respondents and were selected randomly.

TOOLS OF DATA COLLECTION

Data was collected using a structured questionnaire and the respondents were approached personally. The questionnaire contained closed ended questions in order to get ample of information regarding the study. During the interview self-administered written questionnaires were given to the respondent. The questionnaire divided into parts:

1) First part of the questionnaire was containing information of the respondents regarding gender, designations, family size, salaries earning members in the family, and experience.

2) The second part of the questionnaire was containing questions regarding job satisfaction of the college teachers. In this part, we had proposed seven factors (to seek the opinion of the college teachers) which may impact the level of job satisfaction of the college teachers. These are: handsome salary, job security, dignity and social status, job matching with academic qualification, favourable physical environment, vacations and fringe benefits and to work in a desired profession.

The inputs received were analysed and tables were prepared. Further the tabulations were used to calculate responses which resulted to draw the inferences.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

Two types of analysis used in the present study:

1) PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

To determine the characteristic features of the sample, percentage analysis was used.

2) CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

To test the framed hypotheses Chi-Square Analysis used.

We have made diagrammatic/graphic presentation with the help of-

- 1) Bar diagrams
- 2) Pie Charts

VII. PLAN OF WORK

The entire study has been divided into the following six chapters:

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter is introductory in nature. This chapter has been devoted to present Introduction, objective of the study, hypothesis formulated, research methodology, and craterisation etc.

Chapter 2- Theoretical Concept and Theories of Job Satisfaction

In this chapter, we have discussed the concept, definition of job satisfaction and major theories of job satisfaction propounded by different experts. Various related research on job satisfaction has been also presented here.

Chapter 3: Profile of Constituent Colleges in Patna District

Brief review of origin of universities and constituent colleges situated in, Patna district has presented in this chapter. The chapter contains brief elaboration on history, location, facilities, courses offered by the constituent colleges.

Chapter 4: Demographic and Job Related Factors of Job Satisfaction

This chapter identify the personal characteristics and job characteristics of the sample which influence job satisfaction. Personal characteristics of the respondents include age, gender, marital status, designations, family size, earning members in the family, and experience etc. In this part, various job related factors (to seek the opinion of the college teachers) which may impact the level of job satisfaction of the college teacher has been also analysed here. These are: handsome salary, job security, dignity and social status, job matching with academic qualification, favourable physical environment, vacations and fringe benefits and etc.

Chapter 5: Analysis of Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction

In this chapter factors responsible for job satisfaction have been analysed. It further discusses the finding of research, also provide relationship pattern between personal characteristics and job characteristics and its effect /impact on level of job satisfaction.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter contains the conclusion and suggestion for future study. A number of valuable suggestions to improve the level of job satisfaction of the college teacher have been also discussed in this part.

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